

Severity of Diabetic Retinopathy Associated with HbA1c Level: A Hospital-Based Study**Gopal Prasad Singh¹, Suprabha Chandran², Rajiv Kumar Singh³**¹Senior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India³Professor & Head, Department of Ophthalmology, Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Objectives:** The present study was to evaluate the prevalence and assess the severity of diabetic retinopathy associated with HbA1C level in a tertiary care center, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India.**Methods:** Ophthalmic evaluation comprises of measurement of best corrected visual acuity was recorded using Snellen chart for distant vision and near vision using Jaeger chat. A Goldman applanation tonometer was used to measure the intraocular pressure. Slit lamp bio microscopy was used to evaluate anterior segment. HbA1C level estimation was performed by withdrawing 3 ml of blood sample of patient's peripheral vein collected and sent to the pathology laboratory. According to HbA1C level patient were grouped into good control, fair control and poor glycaemic control.**Results:** A total of 50 type 2 diabetes mellitus patients were enrolled. Most of the cases 16(32%) were in age group of 46-55 years. Mean age of the cases was 52.45 ±12.65 years. Most of the cases 34(68%) were males. Mean duration of cases with type 2 diabetes mellitus was 13.12± 1.76 years. HbA1c level of 13(26%) patients had less than 7, 10(20%) had 7-8. And HbA1c level of most of the cases had greater than 8. out of 22 NPDR cases, 7 cases were with CSME and 15 were with without CSME. HbA1c concentration was significantly higher in the NPDR and PDR groups compared to the No DR group patient.**Conclusions:** Older age male patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus patients are preponderance to retinopathy. Increase level of HbA1C corresponds to a higher prevalence of diabetic retinopathy. And statistically significant association is seen between increase level of HbA1C and severity of retinopathy in type 2 diabetes mellitus patients.**Key words:** Type 2 diabetes mellitus, Diabetic retinopathy, HbA1c level.

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Introduction

Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a common complication of DM that leads to blindness. Diabetic retinopathy, which happens when the blood vessels in the eyes get damaged, is still one of the main reasons why adults lose their vision [1]. DMR usually causes blindness in the age group of 20-65 years [2]. DMR is present in 45% of people with both Type 1 Diabetic myelitis (T1DM) and Type 2 Diabetic mellitus (T2DM) [3].

The global prevalence of diabetes mellitus is 9.3%, with approximately 463 million individuals affected. This number is projected to rise to 578 million (10.2%) by 2030. In India, the prevalence of diabetes is 8.9% [4,5].

The complications of diabetes mellitus are divided to macro vascular complications such as cardiovascular disease with 50% prevalence and

micro vascular complications related to the kidney, the retina, and the nervous system, which involved 27% of T2DM patients [6]. Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) is one of the major micro vascular complications of the diabetic disease and divided into two stages, including Non-Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy (NPDR) and Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy (PDR) that occur in the early stage and advanced stage of DR, respectively [7]. Diabetic Macular Edema (DME) has been recognized as swelling and thickening of the macula and is the most prevalent cause of blindness among DR patients [8]. A retrospective cohort study revealed eyes with moderate NPDR, severe NPDR, and PDR were more likely to develop sustained blindness after 2 years of DR diagnosis versus others [9].

Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) reflects the chronic blood glucose concentration and it is used as an index to reflect the average blood glucose levels of the past 1–2months [10]. HbA1c test is the best care evaluation measurement due to a strong correlation between the test results and the diabetic complications [11]. A study revealed when HbA1c was $\geq 6.8\%$, the odds ratio for diabetic retinopathy increased significantly [10]. Another study showed the cut of 6.6% is the best detected for the presence of any DR [12]. Sumner et al. believed that various risk factors could affect the results of HbA1c [13].

The diabetic retinopathy severity be contingent on various aspects, including glycaemic control, duration of diabetes mellitus, nephropathy, hypertension, cataract surgery and smoking, etc [14]. Additional significant factor strongly associated with the diabetic retinopathy progression is microalbuminuria [15]. High grade microalbuminuria is a major causing factor for worsening of diabetic retinopathy. Objectives of our study was to assess the severity of diabetic retinopathy associated with HbA1C level in a tertiary care center, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India.

Material & Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of Ophthalmology, Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India during a period from October 2023 to February 2024. A detailed history and ocular examinations were taken to all subjects, which included checking for any pre-existing non-diabetic retinopathy and maculopathy, non-diabetic renal disorder, previous

laser photocoagulation therapy, and pre-existing neuropathy. Ophthalmic evaluation comprises of measurement of best corrected visual acuity was recorded using Snellen chart for distant vision and near vision using Jaeger chat. A Goldman appplanation tonometer was used to measure the intraocular pressure. Slit lamp bio microscopy was used to evaluate anterior segment. Pupils were dilated by instilling topical 2.5% phenylephrine and 0.5% tropicamide at an interval of 10-15 minutes, with punctal occlusion to avoid systemic absorption, dilated fundus examination was done with indirect ophthalmoscope using 20D lens.

HbA1C level estimation was performed by withdrawing 3 ml of blood sample of patient's peripheral vein collected and sent to the pathology laboratory. According to HbA1C level patient were grouped into good control, fair control, and poor glycaemic control.

Statistical Analysis

Data was analysed by using latest version of SPSS software. Chi square test was applied. P- value was taken less than or equal to 0.05 ($p \leq 0.05$) for significant differences.

Results

A total of 50 type 2 diabetes mellitus patients were enrolled in the present study. Most of the cases 16(32%) were in age group of 46-55 years. 24% cases were in age group of 36-45 years. Mean age of the cases was 52.45 ± 12.65 years. Most of the cases 34(68%) were males. 16(32%) cases were females.

Table 1: Age wise distribution of study subjects (N=50).

Age group (Years)	No. of cases	Percentage
25-35	7	14%
36-45	12	24%
46-55	16	32%
56-65	10	20%
>65	5	10%
Total	50	100%

Figure 1: Gender wise distributions DR cases.

In the present study, 26(52%) cases were suffering with type 2 diabetes mellitus from the duration of 5-10 years. 20(40%) were suffering from 10-20 years. Only 4(8%) cases were suffering from >20 years. Mean duration of cases with type 2 diabetes mellitus was 13.12 ± 1.76 years.

Table.2. Duration of type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Duration (years)	No. of cases	Percentage
5-10	26	52%
10-20	20	40%
>20	4	8%
Total	50	100%

In the present study, HbA1c level of 13(26%) patients had less than 7, 10(20%) had 7-8. And HbA1c level of most of the cases had greater than 8.

Table.3. HbA1c level of type 2 diabetes mellitus patients with DR.

HbA1C level	No. of cases	Percentage
<7 (good control)	13	26%
7-8 (fair control)	10	20%
>8 (poor)	27	54%
Total	50	100%

In the present study, severity of DR as per the modified ETDRS classification. It was found that 18% participants had no changes of diabetic retinopathy. Among NPDR cases, 4% participants had mild NPDR, 24% study participant had moderate NPDR and 16% study participants had severe NPDR. Severe PDR was seen in majority of cases 28% and 10% had moderate PDR.

Table.4. Showing the Severity of Diabetic retinopathy according to CSME.

Diabetic retinopathy	With CSME	Without CSME	P-value
No DR (9)	0	0	
NPDR (22)	7(31.82%)	15(68.18%)	0.0028
PDR (19)	17(89.47%)	2(10.53%)	<0.0001
NPDR (22)			
Mild NPDR (2)	0	2(100%)	0.0833
Moderate NPDR (!2)	2(16.67%)	10(83.33%)	0.0014
Severe NPDR (8)	5(62.5%)	3(37.5%)	0.3329
PDR (19)			
Moderate PDR (5)	4(80%)	1(20%)	0.0719
Severe PDR (14)	13(92.86%)	1(7.14%)	<0.0001
Hb1Ac Level	7.65±1.92	10.12±1.24	<0.0001

In the present study, out of 22 NPDR cases, 7 cases were with CSME and 15 were with without CSME. Among them, 2 cases had mild NPDR without CSME. 12 cases had moderate NPDR. Among moderate cases, 2 cases were with CSME and 10 were without CSME. 8 patients had severe NPDR., Among them, 5 patients were with CSME and 3 patients were without CSME. Out of 19 study subjects, 19 patients had PDR. Among them, 4 cases were with CSME and 1 case was without CSME. Severe PDR was seen in 14 patients. Among them, 13 were with CSME and 1 was without CSME. Mean HbA1C level of without CSME patients was significantly higher as compared to patients with CSME.

Among study participants whose lies between 6-7 HbA1c levels most of them had no evidence diabetic retinopathy. HbA1c concentration was

noticeably higher in the NPDR and PDR groups compared to the No DR group.

Discussions

Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) is one of the major micro vascular complications of the diabetic disease and divided into two stages, including Non-Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy (NPDR) and Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy (PDR) that occur in the early stage and advanced stage of DR, respectively [16]. Diabetic Macular Edema (DME) has been recognized as swelling and thickening of the macula and is the most prevalent cause of blindness among DR patients [17].

In 2013, Cho et al. [18] found that optimal cut off for detecting DR was 6.6 % and moderate to severe NPDR was 6.9 %, which was correlating with the present study where minimum cut off to detect

diabetic retinopathy was noted as 6.6. Similarly, Zhang et al. [19] in 2016, in their study, showed that the prevalence of DR sharply increased when HbA1c exceeded 6.4 %, and their analysis showed that the optimal cut-off for detecting DR was 6.52 %, which was also correlating with the present study. One of the recent studies published in 2019 by Lind et al. [20] evaluated in 10,398 patients, stated that the risk of retinopathy was low if HbA1c levels were below 6.5 % and risk increased with higher HbA1c levels, thus highlighting the role of HbA1c in the clinical correlation of severity of DR. Reductions in blood glucose or HbA1c concentrations through tight blood glucose control in people with diabetes mellitus reduces the rate of progression microvascular complications such as DR, neuropathy, and nephropathy [20].

In the present study male predilection was seen with 68% of males. Singh et al [21] in their study reported that 57.8% were males and 42.1% were females. Kumar et al [22] in their study reported that 55% were males and 45% were females. Santos et al. [23] in his study also reported similar findings. In a study conducted on the Indian population in 2016, it was found that the prevalence of diabetic retinopathy was significantly higher in men (68.5%) compared to women, and it was more prevalent in individuals aged between 50 to 70 years (75.5%) [24]. Another study by Manaviat et al. [25] had a majority of female participants (58.64%) and the mean age of the patients was comparable to that in our present study 52.45 ± 12.65 years. These findings suggest that the gender distribution of patients with diabetes and microalbuminuria may vary and is a characteristic specific to each study, rather than being a characteristic of the entire population.

In the present study, the largest proportion of study participants fell within the age range of 46-55 years, comprising 32% of the total. As this study was conducted among type II DM which was seen in older individuals more commonly when compared to younger. Similar results were reported by Kumar et al [22] that majority of the participants in their study belonged to 50-60 years age group followed by 40-49 years. Eqbal et al. [26] reported in their study that most common age group was 51-60 years followed by 41-50 years. Similarly, Singh et al [21] found in a study of 232 subjects with Diabetic Retinopathy, that most of the participants (69.1%) were in the age group of 51-65 years.

In the present study, most of the study participants had 5-10 years history of DM (52%) followed by 40% study participants with 10-20 years history of DM, followed by 8% study participants had with duration of DM >20 years. Mean duration of disease was 13.12 ± 1.76 years. In a study done by Niveditha et al [27], mean duration of diabetes mellitus was 6.9 years.

Researcher has shown that the risk for DR increased by 1.89 times for every additional five years duration of diabetes. Higher prevalence of DR was linked to longer duration of diabetes, which was also concluded by the Wisconsin Epidemiologic Study of DR (WESDR) [28]. On studying correlation between duration of DM and HbA1c level it was observed that those cases with longer duration of DM even with good to fair glycaemic control developed severe diabetic retinopathy when compared with those with lesser duration of DM in same glycaemic control. Additionally, it was noted that the prevalence and severity of diabetic retinopathy showed a significant increase with longer duration of diabetes. This observation is consistent with the findings of various clinical and population studies [29,30,31] which have highlighted the heightened risk of diabetic retinopathy associated with early-onset diabetes (i.e., longer duration of diabetes).

In the present study, HbA1c level was under very good control in 26% of study participants. There were 20% study participants had an HbA1c level that was under fair controlled (HbA1c between 6%-8%) and 54% of study participants had poorly controlled HbA1c (HbA1c > 8%).

In the present study 4% cases had mild NPDR, 24% had moderate NPDR and 16% cases had severe NPDR. Severe PDR was seen in majority of cases 28% and 10% had moderate PDR.

In a study done by Niveditha et al [27] reported that NPDR was diagnosed in most of the participants, mild NPDR (28%), Severe NPDR (16%), and PDR (10%). HbA1c level was under very good control in 8% of study participants. There were 14% study participants had an HbA1c level that was under fair controlled (HbA1c between 6%-8%) and 78% of study participants had poorly controlled HbA1c (HbA1c > 8%).

In the present study, out of 22 NPDR cases, 7 cases were with CSME and 15 were without CSME. Among them, 2 cases had mild NPDR without CSME. 12 cases had moderate NPDR. Among moderate cases, 2 cases were with CSME and 10 were without CSME. 8 patients had severe NPDR., Among them, 5 patients were with CSME and 3 patients were without CSME. Out of 19 study subjects, 19 patients had PDR. Among them, 4 cases were with CSME and 1 case was without CSME. Severe PDR was seen in 14 patients. Among them, 13 were with CSME and 1 was without CSME. Mean HbA1C level of without CSME patients was significantly higher as compared to patients with CSME.

Among study participants whose lies between 6-7 HbA1c levels most of them had no evidence diabetic retinopathy. HbA1c concentration was

noticeably higher in the NPDR and PDR groups compared to the No DR group.

Patel et al [32] with 120 study participants-based study also find the significant correlation between HbA1c and grade of retinopathy. Therefore, as the severity of retinopathy increased, the mean HbA1c for the level of severity also increased. The UKPDS reported that degree of glycaemic control is the most important component for prevention of retinopathy [33].

In the study, most participants with diabetic retinopathy (DR) showed severe grades of DR when classified according to the presence of clinically significant macular edema (CSME). Conversely, a larger number of study participants had less severe grades of DR when CSME was not present. The distribution of DR severity based on CSME was found to be statistically significant. Saini et al [34] also reported in their study that the distribution of DR severity according to CSME was highly statistically significant. The concept of CSME holds importance as it represents the more severe end of the spectrum, often leading to visual impairment. Analysing risk factors can help identify predisposing conditions and guide us toward appropriate treatments. Chou et al. [18] conducted a study where they found that patients with HbA1c levels of 8.6 or above had a higher prevalence of clinically significant macular edema (CSME). They concluded that strict control of blood sugar levels reduces the risk of diabetic macular retinopathy. Similarly, Do et al. [35] investigated the correlation between persistent diabetic macular edema and HbA1c. They also found that individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus and persistent CSME had higher HbA1c levels at the time of diagnosis compared to patients with resolved CSME. Additionally, patients with bilateral disease had higher HbA1c levels than those with unilateral disease. Our study's findings align with the above research, suggesting that higher HbA1c levels in a patient are associated with an increased risk of developing. Thus, lowering HbA1c values or meeting the ADA criteria can potentially prevent or delay the onset or progression of microvascular complications like retinopathy. Multiple studies have provided evidence of a significant association between HbA1c and DR [36,37]. Another study also established a large relationship between HbA1c levels and the severity of DR [38].

Conclusions

The present study concluded that older age male patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus patients are preponderance to retinopathy. Increase level of HbA1C corresponds to a higher prevalence of diabetic retinopathy. And statistically significant association is seen between increase level of

HbA1C and severity of retinopathy in type 2 diabetes mellitus patients.

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